

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ANOMALIES OF JUDGING IN THE FIRST TOURS OF THE "LATIN AMERICAN DANCES" DISCIPLINE OF "GRAND SLAM" WORLD DANCESPORT FEDERATION COMPETITIONS

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Abstract

Favoritism in international competitions is mainly caused by referees and athletes belonging to the same country. The purpose of this work was to establish whether this factor affects the degree of objectivity of refereeing in the international competition "GRAND SLAM". The protocols of refereeing from the 1st to the 4th round of the Latin American program of the GRAND SLAM WDSF competitions, held in Moscow, Russia on October 26, 2019, were studied.

Since the competition was judged by judges from 12 countries, for each pair of these countries, the average of the points given to it by a particular judge and the average of the points given to the pair by the rest of the group of judges was calculated. Those judges who did not have their own couples on the floor were used as a control group of judges "without their own" athletes. For them, this coefficient was calculated as the ratio of the number of crosses given by judges to the same groups of athletes.

When comparing the judging of the "control" group of judges and the group of judges "with dancers from the same country with the judge", it was found that the results of judging of all analyzed arbitrators do not statistically significantly differ from the results of judging in general. At the same time, it is shown that the difference between the average marks given to pairs by judges from the same countries as the athletes, the average marks given to these pairs by other judges, and the average marks between the "control" judges given to pairs, and the average marks given to these pairs by other judges, is statistically significantly different.

In general, it can be concluded that judges from the same country as athletes overestimate their athletes in the first rounds, and this favoritism of judges in evaluating athletes from their countries can be identified statistically significantly.

Keywords: dance sports, judging, objectivity analysis, statistical methods, favoritism

In dance sport, a subjective scoring system is used for refereeing, which is constantly criticized for its low objectivity [1, 2]. Before the advent of the absolute judging system in 2013, the judging system in dance sport did not change for many years until the World Dance Sport Federation, by analogy with figure skating, developed a new judging system and introduced it in September 2013 [3]. The goal of developing this system was to provide more reliable and objective judging, as well as provide dancers with better information on the specific criteria of their performance. Its basis is the definition of the main four criteria for judging, in which more judges participate and at the same time fewer dancers dance at the same time. Studies show that in aesthetic sports, changes in the refereeing system usually lead to an increase in its objectivity [4, 5]. At the same time, there is a relatively small number of studies on refereeing in dance sport, which raises concerns about the possibility of systematic inconsistency and favoritism in refereeing in dance sport, which may affect the results of competitions [6]. In this regard, it is necessary to study the quality of refereeing when using the new system.

At the initial stages of the competition, with the new judging system, the Skating system is used [7]. With it, the judge must, putting up crosses, indicate which athletes, in his opinion, deserve to go to the next round (i.e., a system of crosses is used at the preliminary stages of the competition) [8]. At the same time,

some works testify that at international competitions one of the factors affecting the objectivity of the judges' assessment is their national preferences [1]. However, in addition to national preferences, judges' assessments are also influenced by other factors, such as the affiliation of a judge and an athlete to the same club and others [9], and therefore, from a statistical point of view, it is necessary to develop methods for isolating each of these factors, in particular, accurately highlight the influence of national preferences of judges on the results of the judging.

Therefore, the purpose of this part of the work is to analyze the influence of national preferences of judges at international competitions in dance sports on their marks. For this, the results of the 2019 Grand Slam (WDSF Grand Slam) competition, which took place in Moscow, Russia, on October 26, 2019 (Latin American dances), published on the Internet, were studied. This tournament does not have a limit on the number of couples from a country, which is valid at the World Championships, and therefore the tournament can have any number of athletes from the same country as the judge.

Materials and methods of research

This article analyzes the discipline is "Latin American dances". The initial data for analysis were taken from the WDSF website [10] (Figure. 1). In this competition, the system of crosses was applied in 1-4 rounds.

Figure 1. Initial data for analysis from the WDSF website [10].

For analysis, the initial data from the site were converted into MS Excel, the encrypted designations of the nationality of arbitrators and countries were deciphered, and pairs from the same countries with arbitrators were marked, as described in an article published earlier [11]. Then the data for each arbitrator and pairs from the same country were transferred to a separate MS Excel sheet, grouped for each pair, and for them, the average number of points given to the pair by the judge from the same country and the average number of points given to her by all other judges were calculated [eleven].

The variation analysis of the series and the calculation of the Student's t-test [12] were carried out using the online medical statistics calculator <https://med-statistic.ru>.

Research results and discussion

Thus, first of all, an analysis was made of the average marks given by judges to couples from the same country and compared with the marks given to these couples by other judges (Table 1).

Since the competition was judged by arbitrators from 12 countries: Belgium, Norway, Austria, Germany, Singapore, Russia, China (PRC), Bosnia and Herzegovina, Turkey, Spain, Poland, and Italy, for each pair of these countries - from one (Spain, Belgium) up to five pairs (Germany), the average value of the points given to her by a particular judge and the average value of the points given to the pair by the rest of the group of judges were calculated. Due to the large number of Russian athletes participating in the competition, refereeing from Russia was excluded from the analysis due to the possible influence of other factors [9]. At the same time, judges from Singapore, Turkey, Bosnia and Herzegovina, as well as Austria did not have their own pairs on the floor. In this regard, these judges were used as a control group of judges "without their" athletes. Similar calculations were also carried out for them, and this coefficient was calculated as the ratio of the number of crosses given by these judges to the same groups of athletes (Table 1).

Table 1.

Average marks given by judges to couples from the same country (1), average marks given to these couples by judges from Singapore (2), Bosnia and Herzegovina (3), Turkey (4), Austria (5), and other judges (6), as well as the average between (2), (3), (4) and (5). GrandSlam - Latin American dances.

Country	Judge from the same country	Judge from Singapore	Judge from Bosnia and Herzegovina	Judge from Turkey	Judge from Austria	Other judges	Average between (2), (3), (4), and (5)
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
China (PRC)	5	5	4,3	4,8	5	4,81	4,775
	4	2	2,3	3,7	5	2,87	3,25
	3	2,3	1,3	2	2	2,45	1,9
Italy	4,75	5	5	5	5	4,84	5
	5	3	3,8	4,8	4,5	4,18	4,025
Poland	4,8	5	5	5	5	4,9	5
	5	4,3	4,5	5	5	4,8	4,7
Spain	5	5	5	5	5	4,9	5
Germany	5	5	4,75	4,75	5	4,61	4,875
	5	3,75	3	4,75	5	4,18	4,125
	5	4,5	4	4,75	3	4,02	4,0625
	5	2,33	3,33	4,67	2,67	3	3,25
	0	1	0	1	0	0,55	0,5
Norway	5	2	3,75	4	3,25	3,43	3,25
	5	1,75	2,25	2,75	3,25	2,95	2,5
Belgium	2,5	4	1	2,5	2	2	2,375
Number of observation units (n)	16	16	16	16	16	16	16
Arithmetic mean (M)	4.32	3.50	3.33	4.03	3.79	3.66	3.66
The average error of the arithmetic mean (m)	0.36	0.37	0.40	0.33	0.40	0.33	0.34

For table 1, the number of degrees of freedom $f = 30$ and the significance level α is taken equal to $= 0.05$ (5%). Therefore, the critical value of the Student's t-test = 2.042.

As can be seen from Table 1, when comparing columns 1 and 6 in pairs, it can be seen that the scores given by judges to couples from the same country are almost always higher than the average scores given to these couples by other judges. However, a comparison of these series shows that the value of Student's t-test=1.35 and, therefore, the differences between them are not statistically significant ($p=0.187000$).

A pairwise comparison of columns 2 and 6 shows that the average marks given by the judge from Singapore to the couples are close to the average marks given to these couples by other judges. Comparison of this series with the average scores given by the rest of the judges shows that Student's t-test=0.32 and, therefore, the differences between them are not statistically significant ($p=0.749221$). A comparison of columns (1) and (2) shows that Student's t-test value = 1.59 and, therefore, the differences between the average scores given by a judge from Singapore and the marks given by judges to couples from their own country are also not statistically significant ($p = 0.123036$).

Further, when comparing columns 3 and 6 in pairs, it can be seen that the average scores given by a judge from Bosnia and Herzegovina to these couples are almost the same as the average marks given to these couples by other judges and, as in the case of the average

marks given by judges to couples from one country, Student's t-test value=0.64 and differences between them are not statistically significant ($p=0.529518$). A comparison of columns (1) and (3) shows that the value of Student's t-test is 1.84 and, therefore, the differences between the average marks given by a judge from Bosnia and Herzegovina and the marks given by judges to couples from the same country are also not statistically significant ($p=0.076077$).

When comparing columns 4 and 6 in pairs, it can be seen that the average marks given by the judge from Turkey to the couples are in good agreement with the average marks given to these couples by other judges. Comparison of this series with the average scores given by the rest of the judges shows that, in this case, the value of Student's t-test = 0.76 and, therefore, the differences between them are not statistically significant ($p=0.454785$). Differences between columns (1) and (4) are also not statistically significant (Student's t-test value = 0.59, $p=0.557237$).

Lastly, for this discipline, we will analyze the average marks given by a judge from Austria. As can be seen from Table 1, when comparing columns 5 and 6 in pairs, it can be seen that the average marks given by the judge from Austria to couples are quite close to the average marks given to these couples by other judges. Comparison of this series with the mean scores given by the rest of the judges shows that Student's t-test=0.15 and, therefore, the differences between them are not statistically significant ($p=0.878462$).

Next, consider the relationship between the average scores of judges from Austria (5), Turkey (4), Bosnia and Herzegovina (3), and Singapore (2), calculated in column (7), and the average scores given by judges to couples from their own country (1) and the average scores given to these couples by other judges (6). Comparison of these data with the scores given by the judges to couples from the same country (column 1) gives the value of Student's t-test = 1.33 and, therefore, the differences between them are not statistically significant ($p = 0.192956$). At the same time, a comparison of these data with the marks given by other judges to these pairs (column 6) gives the value of Student's t-test=0.00 and, therefore, there are no differences between them ($p = 1.000000$).

Thus, we see that, in general, the scores given to pairs by judges from the same countries as the athletes do not statistically significantly differ from the average marks given to these couples, both by other judges and individually by judges from Austria, Turkey, Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Singapore.

When compared with previously published data [10], it is interesting to note that, although the discipline "Latin American dances" were analyzed in both articles, the results of the analysis were quite different. If at the World Championship (WDSF World Championship), when each judge had a maximum of two couples from the same country on the dance floor, the reliability of differences, in general, was 7.2 - 14.5%, and it was

possible to isolate and exclude judges from the analysis with impartial refereeing (without taking into account the marks given to "their" pairs by judges from the Netherlands and South Africa, the reliability was 0.01 - 0.07%, i.e. the difference in refereeing was already statistically significant), then at the WDSF GrandSlam tournament, when not every judge had couples from the same country on the dance floor, but at the same time, some judges had a fairly large number of them - from three to five couples, the reliability of differences was also generally 7.6 - 18.7%, however, such impartial judges could not be singled out and excluded from the analysis. At the same time, it is known that when a judge has a large number of couples on the dance floor, the influence on the scores of other factors increases, such as the presence of teammates on the dance floor [9].

Thus, due to the large spread of average marks given by judges to athletes (from 5 to 0), the use of this statistical method for average marks directly under these conditions cannot clearly identify and determine the reliability of differences in marks given by judges. In this regard, a deeper analysis was carried out, in which not the marks themselves were analyzed, but the difference between them and the average marks of the athletes, i.e. deviations in the marks from the average marks of the athletes. Data for this analysis are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Difference between average scores given by judges to couples from the same country (1), average scores given to these couples by judges from Singapore (2), Bosnia and Herzegovina (3), Turkey (4), Austria (5) also the average between (2), (3), (4) and (5) and the average scores given by other judges. GrandSlam - Latin American dances.

Country	Judge from the same country	Judge from Singapore	Judge from Bosnia and Herzegovina	Judge from Turkey	Judge from Austria	Other judges
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
China (PRC)	0,18	0,2	-0,5	0	0,17	-0,0325
	1,12	-0,9	-0,6	0,8	2,03	0,3325
	0,54	-0,2	-1,2	-0,5	-0,50	-0,6
Italy	-0,09	0,2	0,2	0,2	0,17	0,1925
	0,81	-1,2	-0,4	0,6	0,25	-0,1875
Poland	-0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,12	0,105
	0,2	-0,5	-0,3	0,2	0,17	-0,1075
Spain	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,1	0,10	0,1
Germany	0,39	0,39	0,14	0,14	0,35	0,255
	0,82	-0,43	-1,18	0,57	0,75	-0,0725
	0,98	0,48	-0,02	0,73	-1,10	0,0225
	2	-0,67	0,33	1,67	-0,50	0,2075
	-0,55	0,45	-0,55	0,45	-0,50	-0,0375
Norway	1,57	-1,43	0,32	0,57	-0,31	-0,2125
	2,05	-1,2	-0,7	-0,2	0,12	-0,495
Belgium	0,5	2	-1	0,5	-0,08	0,355
Number of observation units (n)	16	16	16	16	16	16
Arithmetic mean (M)	0.66	-0.16	-0.33	0.37	0.08	0.01
Average error of the arithmetic mean (m)	0.19	0.22	0.13	0.13	0.18	0.07

Just as for Table 1, for Table 2 the number of degrees of freedom $f = 30$ and the significance level α is taken equal to $= 0.05$ (5%). Therefore, the critical value of the Student's t-test $= 2.042$.

Differences between these values for judges with athletes from their countries (1) and a judge from Singapore (2) on the dance floor showed that the differences between them are statistically significant (Student's t-test value $= 2.82$, $p = 0.008553$), judges from Bosnia and of Herzegovina (3), showed that the differences between them are also statistically significant ($p=0.000176$), since the value of Student's t-test: 4.30, the judges from Austria (5) also showed that the differences between them are statistically significant ($p = 0.034691$) since the value of Student's t-test $= 2.22$.

the difference between the average marks given to pairs by judges from the same countries as the athletes and the average marks given to these pairs by other judges (1), and the difference between the average marks given to pairs by a Turkish judge and the average marks given to these pairs by other judges (4) showed that the differences between them are not statistically significant ($p = 0.217829$), since the value of Student's t-test $= 1.26$.

At the same time, in general, for the difference between the average marks given to pairs by judges from the same countries as the athletes, and the average marks given to these couples by other judges (1) and the difference between the average marks between judges from Turkey, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Singapore, given by the same pairs and the average marks given to these pairs by other judges (6), statistical analysis shows that the value of Student's t-test $= 3.26$ and, therefore, the differences between them are statistically significant ($p=0.002849$).

It is interesting to note that this calculation method also makes it possible to isolate the individual characteristics of judges. Thus, the judges from Singapore and Bosnia and Herzegovina as a whole evaluated the analyzed couples more strictly than the entire pool of judges and gave lower marks (by -0.16 and -0.33 points on average, respectively), the judge from Austria gave marks, practically coinciding with the average marks for all other judges (the average difference was 0.08 points), and the judge from Turkey rated the analyzed group of athletes noticeably higher than the other judges on average (by 0.37 points). The average scores given to these pairs by the judges from Singapore, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Turkey, and Austria matched very well with the average scores given by the athletes from the rest of the judges - the difference between them was 0.01 points (Table 2). Judges from the same country as the athletes on average scored 0.66 points higher than the average for other judges, and this was statistically significant.

Conclusion

National preferences in dance sport caused the introduction of a new "absolute" judging system. However, despite this, the national preferences of judges retain their influence at present [3]. The study of this factor, which influences the judges' scores, is still

important, and the method of its detection should be adjusted and refined depending on the characteristics of the competition.

In particular, we see that if the scores given at the WDSF Grand Slam competitions to pairs of judges from the same countries as athletes do not statistically significantly differ from the average scores given to these pairs by "control" judges from Austria, Turkey, Bosnia and Herzegovina and Singapore, then the difference between the average marks given to pairs by judges from the same countries as the athletes, and the average marks given to these pairs by other judges and the average marks between the "control" judges given to pairs, and the average marks given to these pairs by other judges, is statistically significantly different. At the same time, the analysis method based on the assessment of such deviations of the ratings of the analyzed judges from the average ratings of all other judges for each particular pair of dancers is less sensitive to the number of athletes from the same country with the judge participating in the competition and allows you to more accurately establish the facts of the national preferences of the judges during the competition.

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